

Development of a Modular Robotic System for Locomotion and Exploration in Confined Environments

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Abstract—This paper presents the design, development, and experimental validation of a modular robotic system for autonomous locomotion and exploration in confined and unstructured environments. Inspired by tunnel boring machines (TBMs) and burrowing mammals, the robot follows a modular architecture comprising an excavation head, anchoring, propulsion, and electronics modules. The proposed excavation subsystem consists of a drill head coupled with an auger-based waste removal mechanism, while forward locomotion is enabled by coordinated anchoring and linear propulsion. The robot is autonomous, integrating onboard actuation, power, and control through a single-board computer. To assess the feasibility of the proposed concept, the system is evaluated through multibody dynamics simulations using MSC ADAMS and MATLAB/Simulink, as well as laboratory locomotion experiments in a confined tubular environment. The results demonstrate reliable axial locomotion in a confined tubular environment and validate the feasibility of the proposed anchoring–propulsion architecture as an initial step toward future drilling- and steering-capable versions.

I. INTRODUCTION

In mining and planetary exploration, the subsurface holds important findings regarding past geological activity such as the presence of water, and potential bio-signatures. Consequently, robotic systems capable of autonomously navigating and excavating beneath the surface can play a pivotal role in future scientific missions. Robotic platforms designed for subsurface exploration must operate reliably in harsh and uncertain environments while maintaining robustness, modularity, and autonomy. Although several early-stage prototypes for underground exploration have been proposed, most remain limited in capability, autonomy, or integration of excavation and locomotion. To the best of the authors' knowledge, a compact and modular robotic system that combines subsurface excavation with autonomous mobility, applicable to both terrestrial and planetary missions, remains an open challenge. Bio-inspired mole- and worm-like robots have therefore attracted significant attention due to their ability to operate in narrow and confined environments where conventional systems are ineffective.

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Fig. 1: Concept Image of Proposed Solution

Recent research has investigated a wide range of bio-inspired robotic systems for subsurface locomotion and excavation. Snake-like robots equipped with drilling or anchoring mechanisms have demonstrated underground locomotion through coordinated contact and propulsion strategies [1], [2]. Other approaches have explored serpentine robots for operation in constrained environments, including subsea inspection and planetary cave exploration [3], [4]. Complementary studies on modular and soft snake robots have highlighted the benefits of adaptability, compliance, and reconfigurable locomotion in unstructured environments [5], [6]. In parallel, mole-inspired drilling platforms have been proposed to address the limitations of conventional drilling systems in shallow or planetary subsurface exploration [7], [8]. Despite these advances, the tight integration of excavation, anchoring, and modular extension within a single compact robotic platform remains a challenging research problem.

Through this work, we introduce a modular robotic architecture for subsurface exploration that combines worm- and mole-like principles with excavation-head accommodation, pad-based anchoring, axial propulsion, and an embedded gaiting methodology. The contribution of this work lies primarily in the integration and experimental validation of these subsystems within a compact confined-space prototype, rather than in the introduction of a new drilling principle.

The work is carried out through a sequence of actions: 1. The design aspects for the subsurface explorer are decided, and the CAD modeling is performed. 2. The feasibility of the design is verified in a physics-based co-simulation framework based on MSC Adams [9] and MATLAB/Simulink [10]; allowing the evaluation of locomotion efficiency, force distribution, and interaction with confined environments. 3. A hardware prototype of the design is developed. 4. A lab

experiment is carried out to validate the proposed anchoring–propulsion sequence and axial locomotion inside a confined tubular environment.

Apart from full-scale drilling operations, the proposed system is aimed at minimizing excavation effort for targeted subsurface exploration by accessing pre-drilled small entry points. For such operations, the subsurface explorer can be deployed either manually or with the aid of a ground robot at the entrance of pre-existing boreholes. In this work, manual deployment in a pipe that replicates boreholes, shafts, or cavities is considered.

To summarize, the contributions of this work are: 1. the design of a compact modular robotic platform with excavation-head accommodation, 2. the development of a co-simulation framework to assess the feasibility of the proposed anchoring–propulsion locomotion strategy, and 3. the construction of a functional prototype with experimental validation of axial locomotion in a confined environment.

II. ROBOT SPECIFICATIONS

The proposed robot follows a modular design approach as illustrated in Fig. 1, consisting of independent interconnected modules: The Excavation Head Module (EHM), the Propulsion Module (PM), the Anchoring Module (AM) and the Electronics Module (EM). Each module consists of smaller submodules making it extremely modular and configurable for each kind of mission. The submodules are connected through 80° inclined screw holes, ensuring the required structural rigidity and a modular design that facilitates assembly and maintenance.

A. Design of the Robot

The design philosophy of the robot prioritizes mechanical simplicity, reducing the number of moving components to the minimum required for reliable and functional operation. The first module of the robot is the Excavation Head Module (EHM). Core mechanisms and components for excavation, such as the motor, bearings and gears that are responsible for transmitting the actuation and torque, are housed inside as illustrated in Fig. 2a.

The propulsion module (PM) is a linear elongation mechanism utilized during the drilling process and forward movement. It is placed between the separate modules and its linear elongation is achieved using a lead screw with a diameter of 5 mm and a pitch of 0.5 mm due to its high torque multiplication as shown in Fig. 2b. There exist two PMs on the robot, one for pushing the head during drilling operation called Drill Propulsion Module (DPM) and one used for forward locomotion called the Body Propulsion Module (BPM).

The Anchoring Module (AM) is used to anchor the robot in place. Two pads distributed symmetrically around the diameter of the robot are utilized to make contact with the side surface of the tunnel. The pads are designed with an arc on the surface and manufactured from a rubber-like material to increase traction to the tunnel surface. The mechanism actuating the pads is again a lead screw. Additionally, two

guides are added to keep the pad from drifting when contacting the tunnel surface as illustrated in Fig. 2c. The two AMs used on the robot are called Front and Back Anchoring Module (FAM & BAM). Finally as shown in Fig. 2a & Fig. 2b an auger waste piping system is used to transfer the excavated material through the body. The system consists of a rigid actuated pipe incorporating a worm gear mechanism and a passive flexible pipe between the elongation modules.

The robot is controlled by a single-board computer located in the last module, the electronics module (EM). The EM is connected to the main body of the robot through a passive mechanism consisting of three ball joints and three return springs as illustrated in Fig. 2d. The ball joints enable relative motion in multiple directions, allowing the module to adapt its position without constraining the bending capabilities. The springs ensure that, after deflection, the module consistently returns to its initial alignment with the body.

Connecting all described modules leads to a total length of 1200 mm for the assembled robot shown in Fig. 3. The robot weighs 8.5 kg with a maximum scientific payload of 5 kg. The outer diameter of each module except the drill of the EHM is 160 mm while the inside varies from 140 mm to 150 mm depending on the mechanism housed inside. The drill responsible for excavation is inspired by TBMs with a maximum diameter of 190 mm. It directs the drilled material towards the center of the drilling head, where the auger waste pipe transports the waste towards the back, creating enough space for the robot to elongate. During operation, the robot maintains continuous contact with the surrounding environment through the drilling head and the anchoring pads. The proposed concept also incorporates a flexible outer skin, providing environmental isolation and preventing the insertion of debris or small particles into the mechanisms.

Fig. 3: The assembled robot in CAD

B. Axial Force of the Excavation Head

Based on the torque of the motor and gearbox the EHM can deliver forces up to 600 N. However, the target excavation force is selected to 150 N as a trade-off between actuator capability, soil penetration requirements, and structural safety. A finite element analysis of the drilling head under axial and torsional loads confirmed that *von Mises*-stresses and deformations remain below material limits at the selected target force with an additional safety margin of ~ 1.5 , while higher loads approach both actuator and structural limits. This value therefore ensures effective excavation

Fig. 2: Exploded views of the main robot modules: (a) Excavation Head Module (EHM), (b) Propulsion Module (PM), (c) Anchoring Module (AM), and (d) Electronics Module (EM).

while preserving actuator reliability and structural integrity. The generated axial force can be calculated using Eq. (1)

$$F_{ax} = \frac{2\pi\eta T_{ls}}{p} \quad (1)$$

The generated axial force F_{ax} is computed from the input torque T_{ls} , the screw lead p , and the efficiency η according to Eq. (1).

C. Pad Anchoring Force

To anchor on the tunnel wall, the AM utilizes a pushing mechanism with pads that contact with the side surfaces of the tunnel. In addition to supporting the weight of the robot inside the tunnel, this mechanism also prevents backward slip under the axial excavation force. The corresponding force balance for both scenarios is presented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Force balance under robot weight W_{total} .

During deployment, the pads press against the tunnel wall to generate friction according to Coulomb's law. The leadscrew and servo for the propulsion mechanism were also selected using these findings. In (2), n denotes the number of anchoring pads, μ the friction coefficient between the pads and the tunnel wall, N_{pad} the normal force exerted by each pad, W_{total} the total weight of the robot, and $F_{excavation}$ the axial excavation force acting on the system.

$$n\mu N_{pad} \geq W_{total} \quad \text{and} \quad n\mu N_{pad} \geq F_{excavation} \quad (2)$$

III. CONTROL AND SIMULATION OF THE SOLUTION

The operation of the proposed robot integrates multiple cooperating mechanisms to achieve continuous excavation and forward progression. Initially, the robot is deployed within a preexisting tunnel, prepared either by other robotic systems or human operators, and specifically configured for excavation tasks. The primary function is to extend the length of the tunnel, thereby creating sufficient space for forward actuation. During operation, the EHM engages

the target surface while the robot stabilizes itself in three-dimensional space using its pad-based anchoring system. Once the EHM reaches its maximum linear displacement, the drilling stops, enabling the forward actuation sequence. The FAM disengages its pads and is advanced by the BPM. Upon reaching its maximum displacement, it re-engages the pads, allowing the BAM to disengage. The linear mechanism then draws the BAM forward to align with the first (see Fig. 5). This cycle enables the robot to excavate and advance approximately 20 mm per cycle, repeating until the desired excavation depth is achieved.

The simulation environment is created using a co-simulation of MATLAB/Simulink [10] and MSC ADAMS [9]. Simulink leads the simulation and generates control signals for the robot while ADAMS is responsible for the underlying physical simulation. It receives the control signals generated by Simulink and sends the forces acting on each pad to Simulink.

Fig. 5: Proposed locomotion gait

A. Multibody Dynamics Simulation

To be able to adapt the ADAMS model more easily, the model features the same modularity as the real robot. It is shown in Fig. 6 and consists of a drill module with drill (green), two anchoring modules (red and blue), two propulsion modules (yellow and pink), an electronic module (cyan) and four anchoring pads (orange). The tunnel is presented by a straight pipe (white) in which the robot is deployed. The multi-body model preserves the modular structure and mass distribution of the physical prototype.

Prismatic joints connect the pads to both anchoring modules and also the two cylinders of the propulsion modules. These joints fix all degrees of freedom (dofs) except one

Fig. 6: Block diagram of the co-simulation

translational dof. For modeling the passive connection between the EM and the BAM, a combination of a spherical joint and a rotational 3-dimensional spring-damper is selected which restricts all translational dofs while leaving the rotational dofs adjustable when applying force.

To be able to describe the movement of the robot, contacts are modeled between the pipe wall and each robot part. This contact is approximated by a spring-damper system. Additionally, Coulomb friction is applied between the pads and the pipe wall. Contact interactions were modeled using a spring-damper formulation with Coulomb friction.

B. Control Co-Simulation

To control the movement of the joints, MATLAB/Simulink is used. It generates and sends displacements of the joints as actuator signals and receives the normal forces acting on the four pads. The controller is realized as a state machine consisting of five states: contracted, drilling, anchored back, elongated, anchored front. Using these five states, a gait pattern is established. To complete one cycle, the robot must perform the following steps starting from a contracted state where all pads are in contact with the wall. Using these states, a cyclic gait pattern is generated to coordinate excavation, anchoring, and forward progression.

Fig. 7: Actuator displacements generated by the controller

Every actuator can have three possible signals: 1 corresponds to elongating, 0 to no actuation, and -1 to contracting.

This signal is then integrated to generate displacements of the joints. The block diagram of the co-simulation is presented in Fig. 6. Depending on the output of the gait pattern state machine, joint displacements are generated and sent to ADAMS. Feedback to the gait pattern generator are the displacements of the propulsion module as well as the normal forces $F_{N,(bf)}$ acting on the pads.

C. Simulation results

The model is simulated for 10 s. The actuator commands generated by Simulink are presented in Fig. 7. As can be seen, actuator displacements increase or decrease depending on the activation signal shown in Fig. 8a. Each actuator has its own periodic movement cycle which takes about 2 s to complete. In Fig. 8a the forward movement of each module is shown. As the EM is directly connected to the BAM and therefore follows the same pattern, it was left out. In Fig.8b, the drilling force acting on the EHM is plotted. Whenever the DPM elongates, the drilling force is set to the target force of 150 N. After reaching the maximum drilling depth, the drilling is stopped, and the locomotion cycle continues with 0 axial force. After 10 s, the robot has completed 5 and a half cycles which accumulate to a distance traveled of 120 mm.

(a) Module positions during simulation

(b) Drilling force during simulation

Fig. 8: Simulation results: (a) Module positions during simulation and (b) drilling force.

IV. PROTOTYPE

A. Construction process

A physical prototype was constructed. To achieve the necessary force and torque, Dynamixel AX-12A [11] motors were selected. They are capable of providing a peak of 1.5Nm under a maximum load of 1.5 A. For the creation of the components, a Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) 3D-printing process was adopted. Its focus was to create a functional prototype and validate the main locomotion-relevant mechanisms, namely anchoring, elongation, and coordinated axial progression.

Fig. 9: The constructed prototype in comparison with the CAD model

The main body of the robot was printed using Polylactic Acid (PLA), while mechanical components such as bearings, leadscrews, and nuts were purchased. The excavation head was designed with a diameter larger than the robot body to prevent jamming, and the pad contact surfaces and flexible waste pipe were manufactured from Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU) with a shore hardness of 95A. The prototype required 3.5kg of printed material and has a total weight of 8.5kg. Each mechanism was independently tested before final integration. Since no drilling experiments were conducted at this stage, a rigid mock drilling head was attached to replicate the geometric support and contact conditions of the intended drilling head. The electronics module incorporates a Raspberry Pi 4, a servo shield, and the required communication interface. The final prototype is shown in Fig. 9.

B. Control of the Prototype

To transfer the proposed gait controller to the physical prototype, minor adaptations were introduced with respect to the simulation framework (Fig. 6). An initialization state was added so that all anchoring pads engage the tunnel wall before entering the nominal gait cycle. Each servo provides encoder feedback for angular position, velocity, and load, while the propulsion-module rotations are converted to linear displacement through the known leadscrew kinematics and fed back to the state controller. Since no force sensors are available on the anchoring pads, state transitions are triggered when the corresponding pad motors reach a steady condition, identified through convergence of velocity and load signals.

To coordinate the servos driving each elongation module, a PI controller was introduced between the state machine output and the motor command layer. A PI formulation was selected to handle friction, compliance, and backlash in the leadscrew mechanisms, while avoiding an additional derivative term due to the servos' internal velocity and current loops. The controller generates velocity commands according to:

$$v_{\text{cmd}}(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int_0^t e(\tau) d\tau, \quad (3)$$

$$e(t) = x_{\text{ref}}(t) - x_{\text{actual}}(t). \quad (4)$$

Anti-windup, deadband, and rate-limiting strategies were implemented to reduce stick-slip effects. The experimentally tuned gains were set to $K_p = 200$ and $K_i = 0.3$, providing stable operation in practice.

V. LAB EXPERIMENTS OF THE ROBOT PROTOTYPE

In order to conduct experiments with the robot, a transparent Plexiglas tube representing the tunnel is used. The dimensions of the tunnel were selected considering the clearance required for the robot to operate smoothly and not get stuck. It has an inner diameter of around 190 mm, while the inner walls were not made identical to simulate real conditions, and an outer diameter of 200 mm while its length is 1200 mm as shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: The constructed prototype inside a Plexiglas tube

A. Experimental Evaluation of the PI Controller in Robotic Operation

To evaluate the performance of the proposed PI controller under realistic conditions, the robotic prototype was tested inside a Plexiglas tube, emulating the confined environment of the intended operation. The initial validation focused on a single gait cycle, with the control objective of advancing the robot by a prescribed axial displacement.

The linear displacement of each propulsion unit is obtained from the angular rotation of the corresponding leadscrew according to

$$z_i = z_{0,i} + \frac{L}{2\pi} \theta_{s,i}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \quad (5)$$

where $z_{0,i}$ denotes the offset, L the leadscrew lead, and $\theta_{s,i}$ the screw rotation angle. Using the three measured displacements, the head position and orientation can be estimated through a planar approximation. In the present configuration, the displacement differences $|z_i - z_j|$ remained below 0.2 mm, resulting in negligible angular deviations that are further mitigated by the structural stiffness of the system.

Fig. 11: Head position during a single elongation cycle.

During free-operation tests outside the tube, the steady-state positioning error remained within $\pm 0.2\text{--}0.3\text{mm}$ for an approximately 8mm commanded displacement (Fig. 11), corresponding to a relative error of 2.5–3%. Inside the Plexiglas tube, the error increased to approximately $\pm 0.6\text{mm}$ due to higher pad–wall friction and the additional load supported by the leadscrews.

Nevertheless, the system remained stable in both cases, confirming that the PI-controlled actuation and leadscrew-based kinematic estimation provide sufficient accuracy for the intended experimental validation in confined environments.

B. Locomotion Testing

In this experiment, the robot was deployed inside the tube to propel itself through it following the proposed gait controller. The autonomous operation of the mole/worm-like robot begins after the initial movement described in Sect. IV-B, where the robot anchors itself on the tunnel using the pads. The four main stages of the gait controller cycle are shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12: Four states of operation for the robot within a cycle. (a) All pads engaged, (b) Elongated, (c) Front pads engaged, (d) Return to initial length and end of the cycle

The amount of elongation on each cycle is set at the beginning of the robot’s operation. After validating the basic operation of the robot with a single gait cycle, the locomotion performance over multiple cycles is evaluated. In this experiment, five consecutive cycles were executed inside the tube, each with a commanded elongation of 8 mm. The robot achieved a total forward displacement of 40 mm in a time span of approximately 9 minutes for a 4.4 mm/min rate of penetration (ROP). The reported ROP should be interpreted as a conservative feasibility-stage locomotion rate rather than an optimized speed. The motion was intentionally slow due to friction, backlash, 3D-printed leadscrew assemblies, and conservative state transitions selected to avoid anchoring slip during early prototype validation.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the design, simulation, and experimental validation of a modular robotic system for confined-space subsurface exploration. Rather than introducing a new drilling principle, the main contribution lies in the integration of excavation-head accommodation, pad-based anchoring, axial body propulsion, onboard control, and co-simulation-supported gait generation within a functional modular prototype.

The experimental results validated the feasibility of the proposed anchoring–propulsion locomotion in a confined Plexiglas tube. The PI-controlled elongation achieved positioning errors of approximately $\pm 0.2\text{--}0.3\text{mm}$ in free operation and $\pm 0.6\text{mm}$ under increased friction inside the tube. In multi-cycle locomotion tests, the robot completed five consecutive cycles and advanced 40 mm, corresponding to a conservative feasibility-stage ROP of 4.4 mm/min. This speed was not optimized and was mainly limited by friction, backlash, 3D-printed leadscrew assemblies, and conservative state transitions selected to avoid anchoring slip.

At the current development stage, real drilling tests were not performed, and the system validates axial locomotion only. Active steering, sustained motion across voids or insufficient contact regions, and benchmarking under soil or rock interaction remain open development steps. Future work will therefore focus on integrating steering, pad force sensing, inclination feedback, drilling experiments under controlled ground conditions, and quantitative comparison against existing subsurface robotic systems.

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